

NON-UNIVERSAL HUMAN RIGHTS: INDIAN AND AFRICANA PHILOSOPHICAL CONTRIBUTIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF A MORE COMPLETE HUMAN BEING¹

DIREITOS HUMANOS NÃO UNIVERSAIS: AS CONTRIBUIÇÕES FILOSÓFICAS INDIANAS E AFRICANAS PARA A FORMAÇÃO DE UM SER HUMANO MAIS COMPLETO

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ABSTRACT: The main objective of this article is to establish an ecology of knowledge among historically 'silenced' systems of thought as a means through which to comprehend their possible contributions to contemporaneous international human rights law. To achieve this primordial goal, we will highlight a gamut of 'silenced' philosophies, namely Indian and Africana philosophies, which have been violently suppressed by colonial and neocolonial forces. After 'unsilencing' these 'new' worldviews, we will seek to indicate their possible contributions to human rights, a context that has been philosophically dominated by Western modern conceptions to date.

KEYWORDS: Indian philosophy. Africana philosophy. Human rights. Western Modernity. Horizontality.

RESUMO: O principal objetivo deste artigo é estabelecer uma ecologia de saberes entre sistemas de pensamento historicamente "silenciados" para compreender as possíveis contribuições desses conhecimentos para o direito internacional dos direitos humanos contemporâneo. A fim de atingir esse objetivo primordial, necessitamos explicitar uma gama de filosofias 'silenciadas', mais especificamente as filosofias indiana e da África negra, as quais tem sido violentamente suprimidas por forças coloniais e suas perpetuações neocoloniais. Após revelar essas "novas" visões de mundo, buscaremos indicar suas possíveis contribuições aos direitos humanos, um contexto que tem sido dominado por concepções da modernidade ocidental até os dias de hoje.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: Filosofia indiana. Filosofia africana. Direitos humanos. Modernidade ocidental. Ecologia de saberes.

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1 INTRODUCTION

It is hard to unveil and overcome a hegemonic system since the worldview's formalities and contents that support it are directly involved in domination. In this light, the application of hegemonic tools to liberate ourselves from hostile powers, no matter how progressive they might be, seems not enough to impulse radical changes and emancipation. The methodologies applied in this article seek to respect this prior statement, namely Critical Theory, Poststructuralism and Modernity/Coloniality (M/C): while the first and the second will be instrumentalised to introduce our article, owing to their indispensable apparatus to unveil the current liberal systematic predominance and its reified grandiloquent ideas and contexts, the third will play the utmost role in this work, supporting our goal of exhibiting a new project to surmount our egregious 'reality'. Unfortunately, even though international human rights law is often seen as an essential realm to overcome injustices worldwide, it appears to be involved in an atrocious scheme of domination and subjugation of peripheral peoples.

The Critical Theory project aims to overcome the reified consciousness as concerns the grandiloquent ideals of the bourgeois society and the foremost three components of the liberal project, specifically political liberalism (human rights, rule of law, democracy), economic liberalism (market economy and an open international economic order), as well as liberal internationalism (principled multilateralism and peaceful resolution of conflicts) (MARKS, 2008). Further, this theory is characterised by a certain complexity, since its utmost goal is to transcend the status quo and problematize processes of change dealing with many spheres, such as social relations, power and institutions (COX, 1981; COX; SCHECHTER, 2002).

Based on these inheritances, Critical Legal Studies highlight three crucial premises. First, international law arguments are not a logic by itself, but a continuous rhetorical construction; hence, it is essential to comprehend who controls this argumentation (KENNEDY, 1987). Second, international law sources must be envisioned as an interwoven of global sources, not as a sphere of knowledge reigned by consensus. For this reason, Marks (2003, 2008) affirms the bourgeois tendency to treat specific historic forms as essential, obvious and imposed by nature, as a manner in which to legitimate

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its own power. In this light, we must deny this 'fantastic' form as an autonomous international law to contest the *status quo* (see COSTA LIMA, 2019). It is important to emphasize that we must not underestimate the autonomous power of ideas.

Third, this methodology is oriented to those seeking emancipatory changes, particularly oppressed and marginalised groups in society, as this project has been set to develop and identify a set of methods, practices and understandings that aspire to empower lower classes (CARTY, 2008; MARKS, 2008). For that reason, this methodology searches for a subjective/historical conception of truth (see COSTA LIMA, 2019).

As an auxiliary methodology to contest our present reality, poststructuralism plays an important role, considering that it attempts to decentralise philosophical and social discourses. As a manner in which to bring about this goal, it sought explicit textual strategies that a dominant philosophy tends to hide to dominate and totalise a reality and its ontological, existential, ethical and epistemological features. From this perspective, to stabilise this specific order, discursive rhetoric has become fundamental, mainly by the construction of dualities to deny the past, thus seeking to differentiate it from the present-future (FASOLT, 2004; FOUCAULT, 2005).

The formation of historical meaning is governed not by some Hegelian necessity or by caprice but by an epochal play of concealment and unconcealment. [...]The epochs spring up suddenly and just as suddenly give way.[...] They arise like buds on a branch, unpredictably but yet with a certain naturalness and they pervade their time, indeed constituting and defining the age, and then they are eclipsed. [...] they are but touchstones and points of organization around which Being is understood in a particular epoch, around which, as Foucault would say, a certain episteme takes shape (CAPUTO, 1987, p. 203).

When these narratives were socialised, the paradigm of Modernity became the pattern of truth against others, and its core values are imperceptibly introspected in the constitution of each social unit (FOUCAULT, 1973).

We must still ask: how are established values attributed? It is always as the result of a combat, a struggle, whatever form this takes – whether secret or open, dishonest, or underhand. From Hobbes to Hegel the will to power is engaged in combat, precisely because the combat determines those who will profit from current values. It is characteristic of established values to be brought into play in a struggle, but *it is characteristic of the struggle to be always referred to established values*: whether it is struggle for power, struggle for recognition or struggle for life – the schema is always the same (DELEUZE, 1986, p. 82, emphasis added).

The paradigm of conflict and significance have been strong, as, through the construction of a timeline of human beings and civilisational developments, Western societies appear to have achieved a sense of normality, dynamism, and great achievements, against the abnormality, deviance, and primitiveness of non-Western societies. From this perspective, social evolution is legitimated by knowledge, which functions as a form of power; these principles, thereby, demonstrate new understandings of Western experiences and its capacity to join knowledge and power.

Dealing with the M/C methodology, it is opportune to highlight that decolonial theories attempt to criticise hegemonic projects as well as to liberate silenced knowledge and impulse the flourishing of non-Western systems of thought. Western Modernity is apprehended as the historical process by which imperial Europe has begun to build its hegemony worldwide. This rhetoric has created an imaginary, notably since the French Revolution. The abstract principles of equality and fraternity among peoples around the globe are often considered as objective and universalised realities. From this perspective, the three great ideologies of the modern world, namely conservatism, liberalism and socialism, have been reigning thus far (MIGNOLO, 2005; SANJÍNES, 2013). Hence, heterogeneous histories of those who lived under the burden of imperial languages are still structurally controlled by a civilising process imposed by a lineal and future-directed view of history (FANON, 1963).

Modernity does not need to go back to the past except to glorify its own glories, because the idea of modernity is built on the very modern idea of its own past. But that past is regional, local; it is European, adopted and adapted by the United States—it is the past of perhaps 20 percent of the planet's population, not the past of the remaining 80 percent. And *the magic trick of the idea of modernity is that it makes us believe that all pasts that are not European have to be superseded by the march of European modernity, sold as universal modernity* (SANJÍNES, 2013, p. 15, emphasis added).

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Rooted in these methodologies and our previous studies, we aim to give prominence from now to the non-universality of human rights, considering that it is fully embedded within the Western hegemonic project. As stated by Koskenniemi (2008), the idea of human rights was internalised into the Bourgeois State; consequently, the latter has become the prison-house of the former, thus despising and even impeding any subaltern liberating struggles. Besides, international human rights law has also been contemporaneously facilitating the presence and functioning of transnational capital, mainly through humanitarian interventions (BUTLER, 2011; COSTA LIMA, 2020; GOWAN, 2003; ORFORD, 2003).

Present-day international law appears to seek its expansion to dependent and dominated states, both by stimulating liberalisation beyond border controls and reorganising state powers (CUTLER, 2008). In key areas of economic, social, and sovereign political life, dominated states cannot make independent decisions, because they have ceded their powers to international law and its 'global governance'. The prescription of 'democratic governance' offers advanced capitalist states a pretext to intervene against forces that do not favour their economy and their geostrategic interests, as long as it can be established that these forces violate liberal democratic standards (CHIMNI, 2008). Therefore, the language of power is not empowering subaltern classes, as, 'despite the enormous expansion in human rights law and institutions in the past few decades, both the international (north-south) and internal divides have increased and the welfare state is on the retreat' (CHIMNI, 2008, p. 83).

Both the content and the form of international law and more specifically of international human rights law are implicated in Western Modern hegemony (see COSTA LIMA, 2019, 2020). Ergo, by comprehending that the privileges of Western powers are linked to the deprivations of the 'periphery' of the world, we can understand that our subaltern knowledge has not yet been considered: 'Universal' human rights are Western human rights. As a manner in which to attenuate this infamous exclusion, subaltern knowledge must play a pivotal role.

It is opportune to claim that a horizontal dialogue between Western modernity and subaltern worldviews may minimise but not solve this conundrum, since the political-economic realm is still the

foremost and determining context for the maintenance of hegemonies. Nevertheless, at the same time, unveiling these hidden hegemonic privileges and establishing an 'ecology of knowledge' (SANTOS, 2007, 2014) are indispensable pre-requirements to a potential overcoming of our deplorable reality and to construct something prettier in the future.

We must recognise that our objective is enormous notwithstanding, this is just the first part of our work, given that the theoretical philosophical discussion of this article will establish an essential basis to the achievement of the foremost goal of this researching project, which is to contribute in practice to a more embracing and human 'human rights'. In this line of thinking, conforming to Sanjines (2013), beyond that 20% per cent of the globe's population that has been universalising its regional worldview since the colonial epoch, there is another 80% per cent struggling to be heard. Then, to reach our objective, firstly, we will analyse the African (and the Africana) philosophical heritage and its contributions to human rights; posteriorly, we will investigate the Indian philosophical legacy and its significant addition to this Western-dominated context.

2 AFRICANA PHILOSOPHICAL HERITAGES AND THEIR CONTRIBUTIONS TO HUMAN RIGHTS

Before touching on the main subject of this section, it is essential to explicate the contemporaneous meaning of an Africana philosophy:

The notion of 'Africana philosophy' is of very recent origin but is being taken up by increasing numbers of professional philosophers who are African or of African descent, and by others who are not. "Africana philosophy" is very much a heuristic notion – that is, one that suggests orientations for philosophical endeavours by professional philosophers and other intellectuals devoted to matters pertinent to African and African-descended persons and peoples. "Africana Philosophy", then, is meant to facilitate the organizing of past, present, and future "philosophical" articulations and practices by and in the interests of African-descended peoples (OUTLAW, 2004, p. 90).

African signs, emblems, and cosmologies have a deep connection with African-Derived Religious

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(ADR) (ZELEZA, 2017). From this perspective, 'Traditional African philosophy has been profoundly shaped by its intertextual relations with religious, mythic, genealogical, and proverbial discourses that dominate African cultural systems' (HENRY, 2000, p. 22). Religious and mystic discourses, therefore, have philosophical importance.

This symbolic and hierophant approach must not be confused with a magical approach, but a distinct worldview. For instance, whereas in modernity the spiritual world is subjected or eliminated, in African philosophy it is the most important world of existence. This spirituality, although with some important differences among African peoples, must be comprehended as a common system to Black Africa (HENRY, 2000).

Conforming to Henry (2000), despite some differences, the spiritual world is the highest and most privileged realm to the Bantu-speaking Baluba of the former Belgian Congo (see TEMPELS, 1952), other Bantu-speaking groups (see KAGAME, 1956), the Yoruba (see THOMPSON, 1984), and the Akan (see GYEKYE, 1995). Based on this premise, from the analysis of the African ontology³, existentialism⁴, ethical⁵ and epistemological⁶ dimensions, we will attempt to apprehend this spiritual privilege and other features of this philosophical thinking⁷.

2.1 BLACK AFRICA'S TRADITIONAL PHILOSOPHY

Black African ontologies are cosmogonic, since their existence is primarily due to the creative work of deities and ancestors. Grounded on it, the spatial and temporal dimensions of these spiritual ontologies are also cosmogonic (HENRY, 2000). Referring to the Akan people, temporality is not a linear path, but a cyclical one, from the material birth from the spiritual world and its supreme God *Onayame*, passing by death, the return to the spiritual world, until finally rebirth. As concerns their spatial scope,

³ According to Henry, ontology is a comprehensible analysis of the being by our more cognitive activities, thus studying our particular perceptions of becoming, as well as our existence and reality.

⁴ Henry attests that the existential aspects of a philosophical tradition provide a vision of 'being' through the lenses of our lived experiences, rather than by our cognitive activities

⁵ Ethics deals with our conceptions of right and wrong, good, and evil, hence the moral regulating human behaviour.

⁶ Epistemologies are concerned with the problem of truth and falsehood and with regulating the human production of true statements.

⁷ Conforming to Henry, philosophy attempts to explain, elaborate, and defend the truth claims of a specific ontology, thus being often implicitly referenced, or engaged in the production of answers to everyday questions and problems that are being framed in nonphilosophical discourses.

space is seen as the extensive dimension of the project of creation. As a result of this spiritual preference, the ego's existence is a sub existence, considering that it is unaware of the divine message and the creative intelligence of its *okra*⁸ as well as of the deities and ancestors' claims. From this viewpoint, when the ego defines itself within the binaries of its language, it produces deep fissures and irreconcilable divisions within itself (GYEKYE, 1995).

To sum up, the ego has only partial control over itself, given that not only is it externally shaped and determined, but also pre-reflectively self-determined and consciously/reflectively self-determined. It is opportune to attesting that this traditional philosophy does not support a radical rejection of the ego existence but claims that 'each individual ego must recognise its unique spiritually encoded nature and the responsibilities that come with it' (HENRY, 2000, p. 37).

Touching on the existential realm, Black Africa's philosophical thought is rooted in a 'predestinarian reading of existentialism'. From the Akan point of view, the ego's birth erases from memory much of its 'pre-birth' conversation and the heavenly realms in which it occurred (GYEKYE, 1995). In this light, 'individuals who have missed their destiny tracks by wide margins may experience social and personal failure as a result of resistance from deities and ancestors' (HENRY, 2000, p. 35); ergo, when individuals are more fully aware of spiritual claims, more positive and facilitating consequences they will experience.

As concerns ethics, the cosmogonic and communitarian nature of Traditional African philosophy is essential to understand this realm. As regards its cosmogonic feature, an immoral law may only be overcome when deities and ancestors' concerns are successfully internalised within the ontological order (HENRY, 2000). Referring to the communitarian peculiarity, the object of deities and ancestors' regulatory orientations is the well-being of the community. Then, actions that would lower or excessively elevate the position of humans in the life hierarchy will have life-destroying and 'evil' effects.

To sum up, as already pointed out, two different but connected worlds are indispensable to African

⁸ Conforming to Gyekye, the *okra* (the 'soul') is the divine spark of *Onayame* in human's subconscious depths, which escapes our awareness by its determinative powers – 'the unconscious'

philosophy, that is the sensible reality and the supersensible reality, being the latter the priority to the African thought.

The West makes bid to conquer the elements of nature, with the hope that by so doing they would be of benefit to him, but the African seeks a unitized bond with the elements. It is not difficult to see that this divisive attitude of the West has led the philosophers therein to argue about the separateness and sharp distinctiveness between the soul and the body. The African, on the other hand, equipped with holistic conceptual schemes finds no reason why the mind (soul) should be said at all to be sharply separated from the body (MBAEGBU, 2016, p. 5)

Sensible knowledge is the knowledge of the material ego through the function of the senses/emotion/mind based on empirical/rational/intuitive bases. On the other hand, the supersensible knowledge is the knowledge obtained by the suspension of the ego, thus attempting to reverse the forgetful turn that the ego took at its birth; due to this mystical breakthrough, the ego will lessen its ignorance (GYEKYE, 1995; HENRY, 2000). The validation of these claims does not presuppose empiricist or rationalist epistememes.

2.2 AFRICA'S AND AFRICAN DIASPORAS' COLONIAL STRUGGLES

Historical events are often exposed and analysed from a Western perspective. For instance, 'capitalism was born in Europe' (see DUSSEL, 2005; QUIJANO, 2005; SANJINES, 2013), 'the industrial revolution is a British achievement' (see THAROOR, 2016), or 'the Second World War was a war between democracy and totalitarianism' (see BARKAWI; LAFFEY, 2006) are common statements. Though, 'history is never history, but history for'. Indeed, 'what makes history possible is that a sub-set of events is found, for a given period, to have approximately the same significance for a contingent of individuals who have not necessarily experienced the events and may even consider them at an interval of several centuries' (LEVI-STRAUSS, 1966, p. 2-59). Furthermore, imperial, and dependent relations entrench profound complexities to historical analysis. As a result, for example, the metropole and the colony, the North and the South, the strong and the weak, the 'civilized' and the 'barbarian', are all relational and one cannot be understood without the other (BARKAWI; LAFFEY, 2006).

Africana philosophies are indelibly marked by the forces of an oppressive history to date, insofar as Europeans and European descendants' projects have been the only legitimate, while Indigenous and

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Blacks⁹ projects are constantly delegitimated. These encounters and their consequent radical inequalities reflect the political-economic order of our societies. In this line of thinking, the coercive silence imposed by the West over Indigenous and Blacks' worldviews has been depriving humanity of outstanding millennial sources of knowledge.

To shed some light on this perennial 'colonial wound' (MIGNOLO, 2005), Africana philosophies have been playing a pivotal role. According to the Martinican psychiatrist and political philosopher Frantz Fanon (1952), racism from white people towards black people has been disrupting the psychological mechanisms of the latter. Owing to discrimination, in their consciousness, they begin to suffer for not being white; consequently, not only do black people remove any value and originality from them, but they also feel a necessity to follow as quickly as possible 'the white world'. Even so, the utmost conundrum is that, as hard as they may try, black people will never be white; consequently, they are never fulfilled.

As an illustration, Fanon explains that when the negro fully accepts white society (even their physical attributes) and socially ascend in the class hierarchy, he/she will never be completely accepted by it, since he/she will be seen as a 'negro trying to be white'. Even worse, negroes ascension in white society are normally concomitant with social distance from (or/and a refusal of) their 'savage black family'; consequently, these 'whitened' blacks will be seen, from both sides, just as 'negroes trying to be white', but a joke before whites and a traitor before blacks (FANON, 1952).

Further, concerning sexuality, whereas Western intellectuals such as Freud had triggered the standardisation of white bodies as the norm to everyone, Fanon introduced the non-white male racialised body, the black body, which was and still is constricted in colonial and postcolonial contexts respectively, thus an ontological impossibility (RAHIER, 2003).

It is hard to explain, for example, why Blacks' diasporas still adopt defensive attitudes within Western, African and Latin-American societies, although they have never been enslaved, lynched, or experienced any affective trauma. Conforming to Fanon (1952; GORDON, 1995), this is made possible

⁹ In this article, words and concepts referring to 'Indigenous' and 'Blacks' will be written with capital letters, given that we should use this form when referring to peoples. As a result, we attempt to formally 'free' these peoples from the violent inferiority that the English language has been imposing on them.

through a collective catharsis, considering that all the contexts of these societies are controlled by white people. For instance, cartoons always attribute black/indigenous 'characteristics' and actions to evil, from the bad wolf, passing by bad genies until the Devil itself, thus identifying Blacks/Indigenous and their colours with sins (see ALL, 1971). As regards films, the same line of thinking appears to be true (see COOPER, 1933¹⁰; CRUNCH, 1945¹¹; FORD, 1939¹²). Conforming to James Baldwin (2017), '(I) suspect that all these stories are designed to reassure us that no crime was committed. We've made a legend out of a massacre'.

In conclusion, dealing with Western philosophical and epistemological domination, Marcien Towa (2014) has criticised Western theories that aspired to reduce African peoples' theories to an ethnophilosophy¹³, which has been allowing a colonial/neocolonial construction of thought upon Africa hitherto. Although Towa's analyses tend to still endure some anthropological views and to impose a rupture between myths and philosophy, with which we disagree, he is fundamental to comprehend the 'diversified-unity' of Africana philosophy.

In contrast to the Judaic-Christian dogmatism of commandments, Egyptian and Black African philosophies have the preoccupation of non-exclusion of other peoples' values and even Gods (see DIOP, 1978). Owing to this, traditional intellectuals from the latter refused the omniscience and the ethic perfection of any individual or peoples, since, based on African literature, wisdom never achieves perfection and our main goal as human beings is an everlasting improvement. One of the main objectives of Africana philosophy, ergo, should be an anticolonial struggle not only against a foreign enemy but also against all the forces (individuals, institutions, social structures, behaviours, beliefs) that are still its accomplices (TOWA, 2014).

2.3 AFRICANA PHILOSOPHY CONTRIBUTIONS TO HUMAN RIGHTS

Human rights rhetoric is an important support to Western hegemony around the world, since this

¹⁰ In this production, Africans were caricatured as barbarians

¹¹ In this production, Black Americans were caricatured as lazy people.

¹² In this production, Native Americans were caricatured as barbarians impeding progress

¹³ Ethnophilosophy means the judgment of a peoples' production of knowledge from the viewpoint of a specific culture, which result in the subjection of the former to the latter.

scope is profoundly connected to the philosophical economy which sustains our current reality, namely liberalism. In this light, from our viewpoint, international law, both its content and sources, plays an indispensable role as regards the ongoing Western systemic imperialism rooted in neoliberalism (see COSTA LIMA, 2019, 2020). Even though full emancipation of 'silenced' philosophies through international human rights law does not seem possible, we believe that taking these ideas into account may be an interesting reforming approach to minimise the hostile features of our present-day reality.

Africana philosophies are experiencing remarkable developments nowadays, as these worldviews have been rethinking the nature and the dynamics of their self-formative evolutions. As a means through which to achieve this goal, these schemes have not only been seeking to rebuff external and imperialistic analysis of themselves but mixing their traditional knowledge with their colonial experience of deep dehumanisation as well (see HENRY, 2000; MUDIMBE, 1988). As a result, although the white's modernity is still the dominant system of thought thus far, it has become just one more instrument to understand the world among many existing. Re-establishing the linkages between Blacks' cultural demands and their philosophical discourses appear to be a vital pre-requirement to regain control of their self-formation process and, consequently, influence human rights at a systemic level.

As refers to religious rights, Africana contributions may be remarkable, owing to their traditional philosophy. Before touching on this issue, it is opportune to asserting that critical thinkers, poststructuralists, and postcolonialists have already unveiled the Western secularisation 'dogma' of objectivity, which hides new 'Gods' and strong lies of exclusion within it (CARTY, 2008; CHIMNI, 2008; FOUCAULT, 1973; KOSKENNIEMI, 2004; MARKS, 2008; NIETZSCHE, 2001; ORFORD, 2003; SANJÍNES, 2013).

Different from that, Traditional African philosophy does not intend to hide its religious bases, as it claims the superior position of the spiritual world over our 'reality'. In this light, we can contest from this interpretation the radical separation between body and soul proposed by Western philosophy (see LAJO, 2006; REINAGA, 2010), which have been fatal to their ethical scope. The Western closure to their souls has been dislodging these dominators from different potential futures, more beautiful and less

ugly, since reality has become to them an objective reality that cannot be rethought or changed. Concerning Western revolutionary approaches, such as Marxism, reality can be changed notwithstanding, the 'Others'¹⁴ are always made invisible, given that Western experiences, which are considered objective practices, are 'universal'.

The incorporation of sciences and their institutionalisation as forces of economic production and bureaucratic control into the everyday life of Western societies has had infamous consequences, insofar as it has meant a 'technocratic colonisation of identity'. From this perspective, that fall of the philosophic to the technocratic conception of reason has entrenched 'the crisis of European man', eclipsing the domain of spirit and impoverishing their everyday life-world (see HABERMAS, 1987; HUSSERL, 1965). Closing off the transcendental domain has been impeding Westerners to comprehend themselves (the 'Same') and the 'Others'.

Africana philosophies do not exclude other peoples' Gods, since every human being has a different and unique connection to his/her spirit, then variety is a vital basis to this thought. In contrast, Westerners do not see the Other but an inferior self in comparison: the Other always lacks something (see LEVI-STRAUSS, C., 1964, 1966). It is not surprising that this type of discourses is still common to date:

By the end of World War I, more than one million people had been killed or injured by chemical weapons. We never want to see that ghastly spectre return. So today, *the nations of Britain, France and the United States of America have marshalled their righteous power against barbarism and brutality*. Tonight, I ask all Americans to say a prayer for our noble warriors and our allies as they carry out their missions. We pray that God will bring comfort to those suffering in Syria. *We pray that God will guide the whole region toward a future of dignity and of peace* (TRUMP, 2018, emphasis added)¹⁵.

Further, ground on Africa's philosophical communitarian basis, we can claim that inequalities have been entrenching life-destroying and evil effects worldwide. Westerners are still excessively elevated in the human hierarchy since the colonial epoch, which is a direct consequence of their self-

¹⁴ Based on poststructuralism, we apply 'Others' as a synonyms to non-white peoples, in opposition to the hegemonic standardised white peoples, thus the 'Same'.

¹⁵ Part of the speech delivered by the US President Donald Trump after carrying out airstrikes on Syrian territory.

centred philosophy.

Finally, although we will not be able to develop the following ideas in this article, two African philosophies seem to be already applied internationally at some level. First, ancestors and elders are considered indispensable sources of knowledge to the African philosophy. For instance, international human rights law could try to implement, like the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), a permanent council of elders (see OMEJE, 2015, p. 185) to assist law operators during inquiries as regards human rights violations. Second, their profound cultural bonds with nature may place this system of thought in the centre of the current discussions concerning ecocide and sustainable development.

3 THE INDIAN PHILOSOPHICAL HERITAGE AND ITS CONTRIBUTIONS TO HUMAN RIGHTS

Taken at random, human minds from every land seek to understand humanity. In this light, some questions seem to be posed by no matter what civilisation, for instance ‘what is the real nature of humans?’; ‘what is the end of this life?’ ; ‘what is the nature of this world?’; or ‘is there any creator of this world?’ (CHATTERJEE, SATISHCHANDRA; DATTA, 1948). To answer these questions, different systems of knowledge apply their ‘love of knowledge’ and critically investigate a wide range of realms.

Before developing the arguments of this part of the article, we must highlight that ‘Indian philosophy’ is not supposed to be synonymous with ‘Hindu philosophy’:

Even in the ancient writings of orthodox Hindu philosophers, like the *The Sarva-darsana-samgraha of Madhava Acharya*¹⁶ which tries to present in one place the views of all (*sarva*) schools of philosophy, we find in the list of philosophies (*darsanas*) the views of atheists and materialists like the Carvakas, and unorthodox thinkers like the Bauddhas and the Jainas, along with those of the orthodox Hindu thinkers (CHATTERJEE; DATTA, 1948, p. 4).

The schools of Indian philosophy belong to two broad realms, namely, orthodox, and heterodox.

¹⁶ *The Sarva-darsana-samgraha of Madhava Acharya* is a compendium of different philosophical schools of Hindu thought.

Whereas the six chief philosophical systems accept the authority of the Vedas¹⁷ and consequently belong to the first group (Mimamsa, Vedanta, Sankhya, Yoga, Nyaya and Vaisheshika), Cārvāka, Buddhism and Jainism are part of the second group as they do not believe in the authority of these documents (see CHATTERJEE, 1993; RADHAKRISHNAN, 1923).

3.1 INDIA'S TRADITIONAL PHILOSOPHY

From this perspective, we can affirm that the views of other philosophical perspectives have been essential to the evolution of this system of thought. According to Chatterje and Datta (1948, pp. 4-5), 'although there were many different schools and their views differed sometimes vary widely, yet each school took care to learn the views of all the others and did not come to any conclusion before considering (...) what others had to say'. Consequently, 'this spirit led to the formation of a method of philosophical discussion' from which 'a philosopher had first to state the views of his opponents before he formulated his own theory'.

Unlike the West, where different schools predominate until another comes in and replaces it, in India 'different schools flourished together during many centuries and pursued a parallel course of growth'. Mutual criticism makes the Indian system of thought its own best critic. Rooted on this perspective, we can attest that Indian thinkers took into consideration their individual and collective differences, which 'thus conceived to offer different paths for philosophical thinking and living to persons of different qualifications and temperaments' (CHATTERJEE; DATTA, 1948, pp. 11-14).

Beyond their distinct views, they share a common moral and spiritual outlook. First, the aim of philosophical wisdom is not merely the satisfaction of intellectual curiosity, but a practical necessity to comprehend how life can be the best led (how it serves human ends). Every system, pro-Vedic, or anti-Vedic, seeks to surmount a spiritual disquiet at the existing order of things, moving beyond it to understand the source of evils as a means through which to overcome life's miseries. From this 'pessimistic' discomfort and disquiet, Indian systems seek to find hope into the future (CHATTERJEE,

¹⁷ The *Vedas* are the earliest documents of the human mind that we possess, being the earliest known records of social organisation -long anterior to the dawn of Grecian civilisation- prior to the oldest vestiges of the Assyrian Empire yet discovered- contemporary probably to the oldest Hebrew writings, and posterior only to the Egyptian dynasties (...).

SATISHCHANDRA; DATTA, 1948; RADHAKRISHNAN, 1923):

The essence of Buddha' s enlightenment - the four noble truths - sums up and voices the real view of every Indian school in this respect, namely: There is suffering - There is a cause of suffering - There is cessation of suffering - There is a way to attain it. Pessimism in the Indian system is only initial and not final (CHATTERJEE; DATTA, 1948, p. 16).

Then, the faith of Indian philosophies in an eternal moral order is a bastion to their histories. Moreover, the general conceptions of karma and rebirth are also shared among all Indian systems (see BRONKHORST, 2000; RADHAKRISHNAN, 1923):

All of these schools believe that man must be morally and spiritually perfected before he can attain salvation. They also believe that justice is the law of the moral life exactly as cause-and-effect is the law of the natural world. What one sows one must reap. Since justice and moral and spiritual perfection are not achievable in one life, all these systems believe in rebirth, so as to provide the opportunity for moral progress and eventual perfection. Throughout Indian philosophy, from the earliest Vedas to the latest developments, the moral order of the universe has been an accepted doctrine of all Indian thinkers except the Carvakas. *Karma* and rebirth are the instrumentalities by which the moral order of the universe is worked out in the life of man (RADHAKRISHNAN; MOORE, 1967, xxix).

In this light, this law of conservation means that there is no loss of the effect of work done and that there is no happening of events to a person except as the result of his own work. Even though the concept of karma is often misrepresented as fatalist and determinist, free will and personal endeavour are vital pre-requirements to the construction of a better future. Firstly, as a manner in which to accomplish this task, we must understand that ignorance of reality (the real nature of the world and the self) is the main cause of our sufferings; second, by knowing reality, we may achieve liberation by acting well to deserve well in the future, since happiness can be realized on Earth (CHATTERJEE, SATISHCHANDRA; DATTA, 1948).

Scientifically, human beings are considered animals like any other; however, from a standard Western viewpoint, animals do not possess souls, but humans do, which places the latter at a higher

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level in comparison to the former. Similarly, Western secular thought can achieve the same conclusion as refers to this evolutionary continuum by other means, given that the evolution of human beings from animals allows them to be also placed at the top. The situation, nevertheless, is different in the case of religions of Indian origin (SHARMA, 2010):

Together with Buddhism and Jainism, which bear to Hinduism somewhat the same relationship as Christianity and Islam bear to Judaism, Hinduism is sharply distinguished from the religions of the West by its belief in transmigration; the great religions of the world may broadly be divided into two main groups by this criterion, and Hinduism is the oldest and most enduring of the Eastern group, which maintains that the soul inhabits many bodies in its journey through the cosmos, until it reaches its final goal, which is described in varying terms by different sects. The corollary of this doctrine is that all life, whether supernatural, human, animal, insect, or with some sects even plant, is governed by the same law. Whereas Western religions generally teach that man is a special creation, possessing an immortal soul, which is denied to the lower animals, Hinduism maintains that all living things have souls, which are essentially equal, and are only differentiated through karma, or the effect of previous deeds, which conditions the integuments of subtle and gross matter imprisoning the souls and thus leads to their successive rebirths in different types of body. This doctrine of *saamsara* has given a very distinctive character to much Hindu thought and philosophy (BASHAM, 1967, p. 225).

In this light, whereas animals possess souls in Hinduism and Jainism, Abrahamic religions deny it. Similarly, even though Buddhism does not talk directly about souls, both humans and animals are considered sentient beings.

3.2 INDIA'S COLONIAL STRUGGLES

The only permanent result of Alexander's campaign was that it opened up communication between Greece and India and paved the way for a more intimate intercourse between the two. And this was achieved at the cost of untold sufferings inflicted upon India—massacre, rapine, and plunder on a scale till then without a precedent in her annals. In spite of the halo of romance that Greek writers have woven round the name of Alexander, the historian of India can regard him only as the precursor of these recognized scourges of mankind (ARNOLD in MOOKHERJI, 1951, p. 53).

While the West sees Alexander as a great conqueror, India looks upon him as an egregious violator of human rights (SHARMA, 2010). This skewed historiographic view is similarly reproduced by the West

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when dealing with the British colonisation of India. The myths that were constructed to rationalise the European colonisation of non-white peoples worldwide have been important thus far to emphasise the systemic power that governs us. In this line of thinking, as a means through which to illuminate our understanding concerning the violent colonial encounter between Great Britain and India, we must talk about history.

According to Shashi Tharoor (2016), one of the wealthiest and most industrialized countries in the world was humiliated. To illustrate this claim, he affirms that India's share of the world economy before the British colonization was twenty-three per cent; by the time the British left, it was down to below four per cent. During this period, pre-colonial legal systems were disturbed, and punitive taxation completely transformed a prosperous society into one of the poorest nations on the globe. Imperialist historicist revisionism, nevertheless, have been trying to deny the nefarious heritage that the British have left behind since they were expelled from India (see DALRYMPLE, 2017; ROBERTS, 2007; SINGH, [S.d.]):

(Britain's empire promoted) the optimal allocation of labour, capital, and goods in the world (...) no organization in history has done more to promote the free movement of goods, capital, and labour than the British empire in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. And no organization has done more to impose Western norms of law, order, and governance around the world. For much (though certainly not all) of its history, the British Empire acted as an agency for relatively incorrupt government. *Prima facie, there therefore seems a plausible case that Empire enhanced global welfare—in other words, [that it] was a Good Thing* (FERGUSON, 2004, p. 51-2, emphasis added).

Still conforming to Tharoor (2016), the British industrial revolution was only possible due to Indian deindustrialization, which was achieved by the destruction of its competitive manufactural sector and its international networks. Furthermore, he also states that even positive projects from the colonial period, such as railways, the press, the parliamentary system, and the rule of law were specifically designed to benefit the British Empire and to strengthen its rule over India; consequently, that some good came out of it was entirely coincidental, but not a true will of the 'civilizing' project.

One of the foremost issues touching on the British colonisation of India refers to famines. Between

fifteen and twenty-nine million Indians died of starvation in British induced famines. The most famous example, of course, was the Great Bengal famine during the Second World War (see BARKAWI; LAFFEY, 2006; DAVIS, 2001; THAROOR, 2016), when four million peoples died during the Winston Churchill administration:

Nothing can excuse the odious behaviour of Winston Churchill, who deliberately ordered the diversion of food from starving Indian civilians to well-supplied British soldiers and even to top up European stockpiles in Greece and elsewhere. 'The starvation of anyway underfed Bengalis is less serious' than that of 'sturdy Greeks', he argued. Grain for the Tommies¹⁸, bread for home consumption in Britain (27 million tonnes of imported grains, a wildly excessive amount), and generous buffer stocks in Europe (for yet-to-be-liberated Greeks and Yugoslavs) were Churchill's priorities, not the life or death of his Indian subjects. *When reminded of the suffering of his victims his response was typically Churchillian: The famine was their own fault, he said, for 'breeding like rabbits'.* When officers of conscience pointed out in a telegram to the prime minister the scale of the tragedy caused by his decisions, Churchill's only reaction was to ask peevishly: 'why hasn't Gandhi died yet?' (THAROOR, 2016, pp. 258-59, emphasis added).

Owing to this, we affirm that Western genocidal crimes around the world have been historically turned into heroic achievements. Furthermore, genocides seem to have become a huge concern to Europeans only when they were their victims, specifically during the Second World War Jewish holocaust; before that, nonetheless, Europeans were the main perpetrators of genocidal policies over non-European peoples.

People are surprised, they become indignant. They say: 'How strange! But never mind – it's Nazism, it will pass!' And they wait, and they hope; and they shut themselves from the truth, that it is barbarism, the supreme barbarism, the crowning barbarism that sums up all the daily barbarisms; that it is Nazism, yes, but that before they were its victims, they were its accomplices; that *they tolerated that Nazism before it was inflicted on them, that they absolved it, shut their eyes to it, legitimized it, because, until then, it had been applied only to non-European peoples;* that they have cultivated that Nazism, that they are responsible for it, and that before engulfing the whole edifice of Western Christian civilization in its reddened waters, it oozes, seeps, and trickles from every crack

¹⁸ British soldiers.

(CÉSAIRE, 1955, p. 6, our translation, emphasis added)¹⁹.

This argumentation does not mean that all present Indian's problems are connected to the British colonization. However, we cannot deny that the current Indian institutionalized racism, corruption, as well as its ethnical and international conundrums (see SINGH, [S.d.])²⁰ are also interlinked to the heritages from the colonial epoch: the past always leaves marks, mainly a colonial one. Moreover, similarly to Abya Yala, Indians have been seeking to preserve and to highlight their distinctness and traditions within Modern hegemony (see CHAKRABARTY, 2000; CHATTERJEE, 1993; GUHA, 1983, 1985). To achieve this goal, they have been developing new forms to keep constructing the Indian civilisational State, given that 'the contemporaneity of the non-contemporaneous' (see SANJÍNES, 2013)²¹ appears to be a key element to surmount the hostile features of Western modernity worldwide. From these specificities, Indians may contribute to current human rights perceptions, which have been dominated by the Western system of thought and its project of power (MIGNOLO, 2005).

3.3 INDIAN PHILOSOPHY CONTRIBUTIONS TO HUMAN RIGHTS

As well as Africana philosophy, Indian systems of thought may have an important role to transform human rights into a more 'human' context. First, each Indian philosophy takes into account the theories of its 'opponents' as a manner in which to formulate its own interpretations of life; their development, ergo, was and has been dialectical. Grounded on this argument, it appears that the willingness to predominate over other schools is not an ordinary feature of Indian philosophies, considering that mutual criticism is the main basis of their evolution.

¹⁹ *On s'étonne, on s'indigne. On dit: «Comme c'est curieux! Mais, Bah! C'est le nazisme, ça passera!» Et on attend, et on espère; et on se tait à soi-même la vérité, que c'est une barbarie, mais la barbarie suprême, celle qui couronne, celle qui résume la quotidienneté des barbaries; que c'est du nazisme, oui, mais qu'avant d'en être la victime, on en a été le complice; que ce nazisme-là, on l'a supporté avant de le subir, on l'a absous, on a fermé l'œil là-dessus, on l'a légitimé, parce que, jusque-là, il ne s'était appliqué qu'à des peuples non européens; que ce nazisme-là, on l'a cultivé, on en est responsable, et qu'il est sourd, qu'il perce, qu'il goutte, avant de l'engloutir dans ses eaux rougies de toutes les fissures de la civilisation occidentale et chrétienne.*

²⁰ Conforming to Singh, the British division of the former colony between India and Pakistan is the main source of their ongoing conflict.

²¹ Based on this concept coined by Javier Sanjines, we claim that former colonies have the opportunity to apply a new project of intercultural dialogue, recovering 'traditional' peoples silenced past - for instance, knowledge and langue - and expanding an harmonious horizontal project.

It is interesting to underline that current struggles between Hinduism and Islamism in India, which may be used as an argument to refute our prior ideas, seem to have other explanations than religious extremism. As a means through which to explicit our reasoning, we will discuss the issue of conversion in the Hindu religion.

Conforming to Arvind Sharma (2010, p. 39-40), 'as the Hindu sees it, conversion means the adoption of a different set of sacraments in the place of Hindu sacraments, by one who was formerly a Hindu. By "converting" in this manner, the basic assumption of Hindu religious freedom is compromised'. From this perspective, Hindus have no problem to accept the conversion of a Hindu to, for example, Christian or Islamic sacraments, as long as the Hindu culture is maintained. Christianity, unlike Hinduism, entrenches a profound distinction between religion and culture, which is comprehended as an integrated whole by the Hindu. This is the reason why different cultures may profess Christianity, from Europe to Korea, and Hinduism prevails only where the Hindu culture is the most important, such as India. Similarly, Hindus do not accept the Islamic 'total system', which demands strict adherence to Islam, both religiously and culturally; as a result, 'the Hindu has difficulty to comprehending why the Muslim cannot be a Hindu culturally'. Beyond that, we cannot minimize the British colonial and neocolonial influence in this Muslim-Hindu rivalry.

Moreover, Indian philosophies' desire to achieve liberation appears to be crucial to disrupt Western human rights. Since happiness can be realised on Earth, we must first identify current conundrums by a dialectical relation between theory and practice; second, we must try to reform or liberate ourselves from a hegemonic and dominative situation. This 'pessimistic' discomfort and disquiet may play a pivotal role to construct a system of human rights that also respects the Others, who make up more than 80% of the world's population.

The holistic and religious comprehension of Indian philosophies makes us also realise that human rights discourses are deeply juristic in its orientation, although morality is still a pivotal aspect of it. As a result, it is extremely dangerous a society that bases itself solely on law, as what the law gives, the law can take away, especially in a system such as our present-day international 'society', where the inequality of power is intense at all levels, even at the international law one:

The imperialism of international law, then, means more than just the global spread of an international legal order with capitalism – it means that the power dynamics of political imperialism are embedded within the very juridical equality of sovereignty. Formal equality is a powerful weapon in the hands of the state whose overwhelming coercive power will actualise content in the legal form. For the state that knows its interpretation will ‘win’, that it has the power to effect authoritative interpretation, the spread of juridical equality is not only no block to domination: it can be conducive of it. This coexistence of formal freedom and imperialist subjugation has long been a fact of the international system (...) (MIÈVILLE, 2008, p. 125).

Moreover, human rights have been ‘criminalising’ religious understandings as the main sources of conflicts worldwide, while hiding within itself its Christian features (see KOSKENNIEMI, 2008) and its liberal ideology (see MARKS, 2008; MIÈVILLE, 2006), thus supporting Western privileges and legitimating its power worldwide (see COSTA LIMA, 2019, 2020). Leaving too much in the hands of law or base ourselves on a gamut of religious ontologies are not the only paths to be taken.

Finally, Buddhism’s critique of Vedic animal sacrifices and Jainism’s emphasis on vegetarianism, therefore, influenced Hinduism and its development as regards animal rights. Therefore, touching on animal rights, Indian philosophies may positively shape the extension of human rights to all animals.

4 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In this article, firstly, we sought to unsilence ‘subaltern’ world perspectives, which have been violently ‘silenced’ to date by the West hegemony. Second, we tried to unveil colonial and neocolonial myths, thus evading historicism (CHAKRABARTY, 2000)²². Finally, we attempted to conciliate Africana and Indian traditional philosophies with their colonial experiences to analyse their potential contributions for a human rights context epistemologically dominated by the West.

As we were able to demonstrate, an ecology of knowledge could provide an immense opportunity to international human rights law for abandoning its neocolonial features and embrace a horizontal

²² Historicism is the theory that social and cultural phenomena are historically determined and that each period in history has its own values that are not directly applicable to other epochs.

dialogue with other systems of thought worldwide. However, for instance, contrastingly to the Indian professor Arvind Sharma, who appears to defend the assimilation of Hindu philosophies in a 'universal' human rights realm, we tend to refuse the hidden 'objectivity' of this realm, thus claiming a truly horizontal dialogue among different interpretations as a means through which to bring about a more 'human' human rights.

Our main objective with this approach is to retain the best features of each system of thought to construct a new international human rights law and even a new order. It is crucial to affirm that, similarly to China Mièville, we do not believe that international law can be reformed, since its form and content are in close relation with Western imperialism. Moreover, an emancipatory international law within our current political-economic system seems to be utopian, due to the intrinsic relations between them:

Fundamentally to change the dynamics of the system it would be necessary not to reform the institutions but to eradicate the forms of law—which would mean the fundamental reformulation of the political economic system of which they are expressions. The political project to achieve this is the best hope for global emancipation, and it would mean the end of law. *The attempt to replace war and inequality with law is not merely utopian – it is precisely self-defeating. A world structured around international law cannot but be one of imperialist violence. The chaotic and bloody world around us is the rule of law* (MIÈVILLE, 2008, p. 132, emphasis added).

Before the ecology of knowledge changes the bases of international law, these horizontal dialogues may be applied to minimise the imperialist features of our prevailing international human rights law, since we cannot wait anymore for attenuating the peripheral's epistemological and concrete sufferings. Dominators will not simply give up their privileges; consequently, we must take the current crisis of Modernity as an opportunity to be finally heard. These millennial philosophies are indispensable contributions to humanity as a whole.

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